

ENDORSEMENT of EMA

Vaccines are by definition not regular drugs and have not been authorized as such.

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Abstract

In the wake of the Sars-CoV-2 pandemic, some scientists and pharmaceutical companies have come to the unsettling conclusion that the Covid-19 pandemic can only be overcome by vaccination and the constant administration of booster vaccines, at a frequency more akin to the effect of a depot injection than a vaccination. As much as we welcome and recommend all licensed vaccinations (including the rather new mRNA and vector products), we strongly support the critical rejection by EMA of the temptation to keep administering boosters at ultra-short intervals. Vaccines are by definition not regular drugs and have not been authorized as such.

We formally disassociate ourselves from all those who oppose vaccination against the Sars-CoV-2 virus or who are even completely against the concept of vaccination.

Endorsement

Repeat booster doses multiple times a year could affect and weaken the human immune response according to the prime medical authority in the European Union, European Medicines Agency (EMA), comparable to the FDA in the United States. EMA declared countries should stretch the interval time between boosters and limit them to the onset of the cold season in each hemisphere, following the well-established procedure and standard for the prevention of influenza. The advice comes as some countries consider the possibility of offering people multiple booster shots, believing this would end the Covid-19 pandemic, without sufficiently taking into account that vaccines are not drugs authorized as such and have significant effects on the immune system and the patient's immune response.^{18,19,20,21} Israel, not an EU member nation, became the first country to start administering a fourth shot of a mRNA vaccine within less than a year to those over the age of 60. The United Kingdom, an ex-EU member country, announced that boosters are providing good levels of protection and there is no need for a second booster shot at the moment, but it will review data as it evolves; which means more booster doses per person are no a taboo there. Boosters "can be done once, or maybe twice, but it's not something that we think should be repeated constantly," Marco Cavaleri, the Head of Biological Health Threats and Vaccines Strategy of EMA, said at a press briefing in the second week of January 2022. He added, that "we should be careful not to overburden the immune system with more and more vaccinations", and "we need to think about how we can transition from the current pandemic setting to a more endemic setting." Marco Cavaleri therefore believes it is possible that the rapid spread of the Omicron variant could soon lead to an endemic situation. Omicron would act like a "natural booster," he said.^{17,18}

Marco Cavaleri and the EMA have the full endorsement of LCG Research.

Now that, caused by the Omicron variant, the pandemic is rapidly evolving into a endemic the times of quite deadly waves will come to an end. As we elaborated in an earlier paper we staunchly believe that Sars-CoV-2 will become the fifth endemic human coronavirus (hCoV type Sars-CoV-2 type Omicron) in 2022. However, this will by no means make vaccinations and novel drugs obsolete.^{1,6} However the pandemic as the world knew it until January 2022 is fading away, with Sars-CoV-2 type Omicron becoming a regular winter season virus. The infectivity of the Omicron variant is exceptionally high (with an R0 value of possibly ~10), so the likelihood of an even more infectious variant (including other, theoretically possible serotypes) approaches zero.^{14,15,16} Omicron actually appears to cause only clinically rather mild disease in vaccinated and recovered individuals.¹ We assume that Omicron - unlike the Delta variant - is able to induce a partial immunity against other coronaviruses, especially in those who are vaccinated or already had Covid-19 or hCoV 229E.^{2,6} Most likely this was also the case in a precursor pandemic (the "Russian Flu", 1889-1895), which was probably by coronavirus OC43. It was clinically similar to Covid-19 and has been endemic as a less dangerous but still potent human coronavirus (hCoV) since 1895 - still causing severe outbreaks and providing a possible example of how a coronavirus pandemic can come to an end.^{10,11,12} What is more, it is not entirely impossible that the comparatively mild course of the Omicron variant is caused by cross-immunity.³ For example, Omicron may have inherited genetic material from endemic hCoV 229E during its emergence.² Herd immunity is unlikely for Sars-CoV-2⁴ (as for all the other endemic hCoVs), but a wide cross-immunity effect, resembling something similar to herd immunity, may occur. The danger of endemic human coronaviruses (hCoVs) is generally underestimated.^{7,8,9} Sars-CoV-2 shares typical coronavirus characteristics with other coronaviruses and is not a singularity.^{5,7,9} Every year, thousands of mainly elderly and debilitated people become most severely ill from one of the

known “traditional” endemic human coronaviruses (hCoVs), while others experience these pathogens only as causes of a flu-like infection.⁹ Despite the dangerous nature of pneumonia caused by human coronaviruses, these pathogens are unknown to the general population, unlike influenza, or are being grossly mislabeled as “cold viruses”.^{7,8,9}

The development of Sars-CoV-2 vaccines is certainly a milestone in the history of science. However, the belief that ‘vaccinating out of the pandemic’ with vaccines which do not produce sterile immunity was a pretty bold assumption. Similarly, the mutational propensity of coronaviruses was apparently persistently underestimated and the power of the vaccines was initially over-estimated. The reasons for this remains unclear to date. What is certain, however, is that the enormous promises of efficacy that were initially made¹³ and communicated to the general public were untenable - foreseeably untenable, if one is even rudimentarily familiar with the basic ‘behavior’ of coronaviruses. However, there is little room for doubt that the vaccinations very often prevent severe courses of Sars-CoV-2 type Omicron in people at risk.³

There was also irritation regarding the propagation of herd immunity as a goal, since such immunity is simply not known for coronaviruses.⁴ What is known, however, are certain variants that induce so-called cross-immunity better than other variants. Thus, logically, repeated contact with some coronaviruses and their variants (now also with vaccinations) leads to an increasingly complex cross-immunity, so that a dangerous coronavirus can become a relatively mild one, measured by symptom severity. Based on the aforementioned facts and additional findings as well as observations, the community-relevant aspects of the Sars-CoV-2 pandemic currently appears to be nearing its end. But the virus will remain. As Omicron or future Omicron variants it will quickly join the arsenal of endemic coronaviruses, and with a R0 of 10 competing variants, even other serotypes will most likely be no issue.

However, the hCoVs are not banal cold viruses but potent pathogens that cause hundreds of thousands of pneumonias every year, especially in winter, and which are not infrequently fatal in weakened and elderly people.⁹ It would therefore be wise for vaccine manufacturers to focus on a vaccine against the endemic coronaviruses⁷ now that viable biotechnological platforms exist. We do not believe that a separate vaccine against Omicron is necessary, even in the case of the emerging of new serotypes as long as their infectivity is lower than that of Omicron.⁶ Rather, a vaccination strategy is needed that covers the known and relevant Sars-CoV-2 variants as well as the four hCoVs that have been known for some time. This would bring the Covid-19 pandemic to a favorable end, and the new technologies accelerated by the pandemic could save many lives year after year in the future. However, this would require slowly lowering the alert mode for Sars-CoV-2 type Omicron now, and motivating as well as supporting vaccine manufacturers to develop broader-acting vaccines (with less risks and side-effects) which can be administered alongside the yearly influenza vaccine. This also applies to the new drugs against coronavirus diseases. For this important step towards endemicity, a rapid alignment with reality and an end to panic mode is as important as it is desirable.

Conflicts of interest

none

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